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Mineral trapping of CO₂ for cement industry de-carbonization

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Abstract

Mineralization of carbon dioxide by alkaline industrial wastes is a promising carbon capture and storage method. The Estonian oil shale based energy sector is the source of substantial CO₂ emissions as well as the formation of huge amounts of burnt oil shale (7.2 Mt annually). Retention capacity of these wastes is about 0.1 t of CO₂ per t of ash. In addition, concrete demolition wastes, specifically the fine fractions rich in calcium hydroxide and calcium silicate hydrate, are also considered to be good sorbents for CO₂ sequestration, forming thermodynamically stable calcium carbonate.

The objective of current research is to study burnt oil shale and concrete demolition wastes as sorbents in CO₂ mineralization process in order to identify the most promising materials for CO₂ capture as well as to specify reaction kinetics and operating parameters for a scale up. Results indicated that selected types of burnt oil shale could be used as effective binders in the proposed CO₂-mineralization system. The CO₂ uptake was mainly attributed by the free lime content, which is relatively high (10-15%) in burnt oil shale, but nonexistent in concrete demolition wastes. A kinetic model was built to predict the composition of solid and gas phase at given operating conditions. The re-carbonated materials could in turn be used in concrete application, so the CO₂ captured from the Ca-looping installation in Vernasca Cement Plant could be trapped and utilized in the same plant.

Keywords: burnt oil shale; CO₂ mineralization; concrete demolition waste

1. Introduction

Mineralization of gaseous CO₂ into thermodynamically stable carbonates is one of the carbon capture and storage methods of interest. In particular, using solid wastes generated from large scale industrial processes has a number of advantages, as these materials are forming often in vicinity of CO₂ point source emissions, supply a readily available source of CaO and/or Ca-silicates without the need for mining, they are usually fine-grained with high surface areas, and the end product may be reusable in construction materials [1]. The Republic of Estonia is in a unique position due to its oil shale based energy sector. About 7.2 Mt of burnt oil shale (BOS) [2-4], consisting 5-20% of free lime [5, 6], is formed annually in the heat and power production.

Another type of waste, concrete demolition waste (CDW), contains considerable amount (10-15%) of cement hydrate that could bind CO₂ improving also the quality of the concrete slurry waste for concrete application [7]. Specifically, fine fractions of CDW are generally characterized by a higher amount of the cement hydrate (25-30%) enabling a high trapping potential for CO₂ [8]. Considering that around 0.87 ton of CO₂ is emitted for every ton of

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cement produced, the cement industry is globally responsible for up to 7% of annual anthropogenic CO₂ emissions [9]. By using accelerated carbonation, it is possible to improve the quality of recycled concrete aggregate and waste cement as well as balance the CO₂ cycle. According to International Energy Agency (IEA, <https://www.iea.org/>) and EU Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP, <http://www.zeroemissionsplatform.eu/>) studies, cement industry should contribute to the largest CO₂ emissions reduction through carbon capture and storage in Europe, in order to meet the target of 2°C of global temperature increase.

The objective of this research is to study waste BOS and CDW as sorbents in CO₂ wet mineralization process in order to identify the most promising materials for CO₂ capture and specify reaction kinetics and operating parameters for a scale up. Current study is carried out as a part of HORIZON 2020 project Clean clinker production by Calcium looping process (CLEANKER). The mineralization pilot is planned to use CO₂ captured from the Ca-looping demo system in Vernasca Cement Plant. The re-carbonated wastes will be tested via concrete casting in order to demonstrate the quality of the commercial product in the following stages of the CLEANKER project.

Nomenclature

BET SSA	specific surface area (Brunauer-Emmett-Teller adsorption method)
BOS	burnt oil shale
CDW	concrete demolition waste
fCaO	free lime content
PP	power plant

2. Data and methods

2.1. Characterization of materials

Solid wastes from power and cement sectors were utilized in CO₂ mineralization process. The BOS1, BOS3 and BOS7 represent burnt oil shale samples from electrostatic precipitators (ESPA) and BOS2, BOS4 and BOS8 represent burnt oil shale samples from total ash silo of circulating fluidized bed boilers of Eesti, Balti and Auvere power plants (PP), respectively [10]. The pulverized firing burnt oil shale sample BOS5 was collected from an SO₂ removal system (Novel Integrated Desulphurization, Alstom Power). The BOS6 sample was collected from Enefit280 units that produce shale oil [11]. Two different suppliers of concrete demolition wastes made their material available for testing: I.L.C. s.r.l (Rondissone, TO) and Isoltrasporti (Isola Sant'Antonio, AL). Different types of materials were delivered: fine fraction of recycled demolition waste (CDW1 and CDW3), fine fraction from demolition waste selectively derived from concrete (CDW2) and fine fraction of recycled demolition waste submitted to washing process (CDW4).

The materials were analyzed using quantitative X-ray diffraction (XRD, Bruker D8 Advanced). The contents of free lime (fCaO, ethylene glycol method [12]) and total carbon (Electra CS - 580 Carbon/ Sulfur Determinator) were determined. In addition, the BET specific surface area and the particle size distribution was determined using a Kelvin 1042 sorptometer and Horiba laser scattering particle size distribution analyser LA-950, respectively.

In order to estimate and compare the CO₂ binding ability of different materials the CO_{2,max}, the maximal possible CO₂ content of the sample, was calculated on the basis of CO₂, fCaO, CaSiO₃, Ca₂SiO₄ and Ca₃Mg(SiO₄)₂ content of initial sample.

$$CO_{2,max} = \frac{\frac{fCaO \times M_{CO_2}}{M_{CaO}} + \frac{CaSiO_3 \times M_{CO_2}}{M_{CaSiO_3}} + \frac{2 \times Ca_2SiO_4 \times M_{CO_2}}{M_{Ca_2SiO_4}} + \frac{3 \times Ca_3Mg(SiO_4)_2 \times M_{CO_2}}{M_{Ca_3Mg(SiO_4)_2}} + CO_2}{100 + \frac{fCaO \times M_{CO_2}}{M_{CaO}} + \frac{CaSiO_3 \times M_{CO_2}}{M_{CaSiO_3}} + \frac{2 \times Ca_2SiO_4 \times M_{CO_2}}{M_{Ca_2SiO_4}} + \frac{3 \times Ca_3Mg(SiO_4)_2 \times M_{CO_2}}{M_{Ca_3Mg(SiO_4)_2}}} \times 100, \%$$

2.2. Experimental procedure

The experiments were carried out in wet route conditions [13] – $L/S=0.2$, using semi-batch Eirich EL1 type intensive mixer shown in Fig. 1. The wastes were treated under different operating regimes by varying rotation speed from 300 to 3000 rpm, CO_2 concentration in model gas from 20 to 70% (from Ca-looping pilot), gas flow from 30 to 400 L/h and the mass of initial sample from 150 to 600 g, Table 1.

Table 1. Operating regimes

Sample	Explanation	$CO_2\%$ in gas	V(gas), L/h	m(ash), g	Rotation speed, rpm
Burnt oil shale					
BOS1	Eesti PP ESPA1	20→70	30→200	200	300→3000
BOS2	Eesti PP total	20→70	30→200	200	300→3000
BOS3	Balti PP ESPA1	20→70	30→400	200→600	300→3000
BOS4	Balti PP total	20→70	30→200	200	300→3000
BOS5	DeSO _x	20→70	30→200	200	300→3000
BOS6	Enefit280 total	20	100	200	3000
BOS7	Auvere PP ESPA1	20→70	30→400	200→600	300→3000
BOS8	Auvere PP total	20→70	30→200	200	300→3000
Concrete demolition waste					
CDW2	I.L.C. s.r.l (Rondissone, TO)	20→70	30→200	200	300→3000

Fig. 1. Experimental setup

The CO_2 content in gas phase was detected by Doutec infrared analyzer and the carbonated samples were dried in thermostat for 3 h at $105^\circ C$ and analyzed for total carbon and free lime content as the main indicators for the carbonation process.

2.3. Modeling software

Process modeling was carried out using ASPEN Plus V8.6 (APV86) software, which is a process modeling tool for conceptual design, optimization, and performance monitoring widely used in the chemical, mining, and solid fuel power generation industries [14].

3. Results and discussion

The laboratory tests on BOS and CDW carbonation were carried out in order to identify the most promising materials for CO₂ capture and to build a kinetic model. The main objective was to work out recommendations for the construction and operation of a large (up to 1000 L) device for mineralization of CO₂ from the Vernasca demonstration plant, using selected types of BOS as well as CDW from different locations.

Fig. 2. Phase composition of initial materials.

Fig. 3. Maximal possible CO₂ content of initial samples

The phase composition indicated that the BOS samples (apart from BOS6) contained a considerable amount lime, portlandite and secondary Ca-silicates, which attribute as potential CO₂ binders (Fig. 2). In CDW samples supplied by I.L.C. (CDW1 and CDW2) quartz and silicates accounted for about 80% of the total mineral composition. Samples supplied by Isoltrasporti (CDW3 and CDW4) had a much higher amount of carbonates against a lower content of silicates, while the quantity of quartz was similar. The same tendencies are shown on

Fig. 3, where the gap between the initial and maximum CO_2 determines the theoretical binding capacity. Most of BOS samples have quite good CO_2 binding potential, but the CO_2 binding capacity of CDW and BOS6 samples is already depleted.

Fig. 4. Wet carbonation of different samples: changes in Ca(OH)_2 and CaCO_3 concentration (on left) and CO_2 concentration in off-gas (on right) during carbonation of different samples (70% CO_2 in model gas, $V_{\text{gas}} = 200$ L/h, $m(\text{ash}) = 300$ g, rotation speed 300 rpm, $L/S=0.2$).

Carbonation tests showed that the free lime content could be exhausted with 30 min in the conditions of low range water to solid ratio (0.2 w/w) and gas flow of 70% CO_2 in air (Fig. 4). The CO_2 uptake was mainly attributed by the free lime content, which is relatively high (10-15%) in BOS, but non-existent in concrete demolition wastes. Tests with different samples indicated that free lime content was almost fully utilized in case of electrostatic precipitator ashes BOS3 and BOS7, characterized by small particle size and relatively high specific surface area ($d_{\text{mean}} = 21 \mu\text{m}$ and $\text{SSA} = 6.05 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ in case of BOS7). The CaCO_3 content achieved the highest values in case of total ash BOS4 due to its initial carbonate content (Fig. 2), but coarser particle size inhibits the accessibility of free lime. Carbonation of BOS5 is inhibited due to low surface area ($\text{SSA} = 1.77 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) and molten phase capsuling the free lime, which is typical for PF ashes (6).

In order to increase the reactor efficiency, the material flows in 1 L semi-batch reactor were increased step by step from 150 to 600 g ash and 30 to 400 L/h gas. Changing different parameters indicated that increasing sample mass (Fig. 5) and gas flow rate (Fig. 6) accelerated the wet carbonation process, as changing the mixing speed from 300 to 3000 rpm had negligible effect. Increased mass flows led to significant temperature rise in the reactor, because both lime slaking and carbonation reactions are exothermic. On the other hand, slight temperature rise enhances reaction kinetics. In case of the test with 600 g of ash and 400 L/h of model gas, 60 mL of water had to be added in every 5 minutes to compensate the moisture loss due to evaporation. Therefore, in case of process upscale the reactor temperature has to be monitored and controlled to avoid overheating and maintain the optimal water to liquid ratio.

Fig. 5. The effect of sample mass in 1 L reactor: changes in Ca(OH)_2 and CaCO_3 concentration in solid phase and CO_2 concentration in off-gas during carbonation of BOS7 (70% CO_2 in model gas, $V_{\text{gas}} = 400 \text{ L/h}$, rotation speed 300 rpm, $L/S=0.2$).

Fig. 6. The effect of gas flow rate in 1 L reactor: changes in Ca(OH)_2 and CaCO_3 concentration in solid phase and CO_2 concentration in off-gas during carbonation of BOS7 (70% CO_2 in model gas, $m(\text{ash}) = 600 \text{ g}$, rotation speed 300 rpm, $L/S=0.2$).

A kinetic model built on Ca(OH)_2 dissolution [15] and carbonation [16] was implemented within the Aspen Plus simulation platform by inserting the chemical reactions and corresponding kinetic constants shown in Table 2 into the RBatch reactor model ($t=25^\circ\text{C}$, $P=1 \text{ bar}$, $Q= 0 \text{ Gcal/hr}$). The model followed the experimental results for Ca(OH)_2 content during carbonation but underestimated the carbonate content in solid phase (Fig. 7). This is due to Ca-silicates (Fig. 2) that also contribute to CO_2 binding but were not consider in this model.

Table 2. Kinetic reaction model

No	Stoichiometry	k
1	$\text{CO}_2(\text{MIXED}) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{HCO}_3^-(\text{MIXED}) + \text{H}^+(\text{MIXED})$	$2.4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$
2	$\text{H}^+(\text{MIXED}) + \text{HCO}_3^-(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{CO}_2(\text{MIXED}) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{MIXED})$	$5.7 \times 10^4 \text{ L}(\text{mol} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$
3	$\text{CO}_2(\text{MIXED}) + \text{OH}^-(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{HCO}_3^-(\text{MIXED})$	$8.4 \times 10^3 \text{ L}(\text{mol} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$
4	$\text{HCO}_3^-(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{OH}^-(\text{MIXED}) + \text{CO}_2(\text{MIXED})$	$2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$
5	$\text{OH}^-(\text{MIXED}) + \text{H}^+(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{MIXED})$	$1.4 \times 10^{11} \text{ L}(\text{mol} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$
6	$\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{OH}^-(\text{MIXED}) + \text{H}^+(\text{MIXED})$	$1.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}(\text{L} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$
7	$\text{HCO}_3^-(\text{MIXED}) + \text{OH}^-(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{CO}_3^{2-}(\text{MIXED}) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{MIXED})$	$6 \times 10^9 \text{ L}(\text{mol} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$
8	$\text{CO}_3^{2-}(\text{MIXED}) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{HCO}_3^-(\text{MIXED}) + \text{OH}^-(\text{MIXED})$	$1.2 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$
9	$\text{Ca}^{2+}(\text{MIXED}) + \text{CO}_3^{2-}(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{CaCO}_3(\text{CISOLID})$	$1.9 \times 10^6 \text{ L}(\text{mol} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$
10	$\text{CaCO}_3(\text{CISOLID}) \rightarrow \text{Ca}^{2+}(\text{MIXED}) + \text{CO}_3^{2-}(\text{MIXED})$	$9.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}(\text{L} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$
11	$\text{CaCO}_3(\text{CISOLID}) + \text{H}^+(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{Ca}^{2+}(\text{MIXED}) + \text{HCO}_3^-(\text{MIXED})$	$0.1 \times 10^7 \text{ s}^{-1}$
12	$\text{Ca}^{2+}(\text{MIXED}) + \text{HCO}_3^-(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{CaCO}_3(\text{CISOLID}) + \text{H}^+(\text{MIXED})$	$0.4 \times 10^3 \text{ L}(\text{mol} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$
13	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2(\text{CISOLID}) \rightarrow \text{Ca}^{2+}(\text{MIXED}) + 2 \text{ OH}^-(\text{MIXED})$	$1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$
14	$\text{Ca}^{2+}(\text{MIXED}) + 2 \text{ OH}^-(\text{MIXED}) \rightarrow \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2(\text{CISOLID})$	$508.0 \text{ L}(\text{mol} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$

Fig. 5. Simulation vs experiment: changes in $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and CaCO_3 concentration in solid phase (on left) and CO_2 concentration in off-gas (on right) during carbonation of BOS3 and BOS7 (70% CO_2 in model gas, $V_{\text{gas}} = 400 \text{ L/h}$, $m(\text{ash}) = 600 \text{ g}$, rotation speed 300 rpm, $L/S=0.2$).

The rate and extent of CO_2 mineralization process depends mainly on the characteristics of available waste material. This model applies for electrostatic precipitator ashes that contain easily accessible free lime. For more complicated cases that include capsulated reactive species and/or Ca-silicates as the main CO_2 binders, the operating conditions as well as the model have to be modified. The model also predicts the reactor temperature, ion composition and pH of the reaction mixture.

4. Conclusions

Different types of burnt oil shale and concrete demolition wastes were tested via wet route direct carbonation. Tests showed that the free lime content could be exhausted with 30 min in the conditions of low range water to solid ratio (0.2 w/w) and gas flow of 70% CO_2 in air. The CO_2 uptake was mainly attributed by the free lime content, which is relatively high (10-15%) in BOS, but nonexistent in CDW samples. Comparing different types of BOS

samples indicated that free lime content was almost fully utilized in case of electrostatic precipitator ashes from CFB boilers, as the free lime in coarser total ashes and non-porous pulverized firing ashes was only partially utilized. Changing different parameters indicated that increasing sample mass and gas flow rate accelerated the wet carbonation process, as changing the mixing speed from 300 to 3000 rpm had negligible effect.

A kinetic model was built to predict the composition of solid and gas phase at given operating conditions. The model followed the experimental results for $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ content during carbonation but underestimated the carbonate content in solid phase. This is due to Ca-silicates that also contribute to CO_2 binding but were not considered in this model.

Based on the results, selected types of burnt oil shale could be used as effective sorbents in the proposed CO_2 -mineralization process, binding up to 0.18 kg CO_2 per kg of waste. Utilizing re-carbonated wastes in concrete application supports closing the CO_2 cycle of a cement plant by trapping the carbon dioxide into concrete.

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